

IONIQA's PET depolymerisation story: from bottles to Multi-Layer Trays and beyond

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Abstract: Current environmental needs make developments in the field of plastic recycling increasingly urgent, as plastics consumption keeps increasing while governmentally set recycling targets are far out of reach. Impurities containing plastic waste needs to be fed to recycling processes, which in their turn require to produce virgin quality like materials as output. Feedstock impurities can be of any kind; either as part of the composition of the feed due to sorting efficiencies or as high- or low molecular weight additives and degradation products. These impurities in the feedstock make traditional mechanical recycling only applicable to a certain percentage of the plastic waste flakes available on the market. Chemical recycling can be a solution to this challenge as it can handle higher impurity levels in waste plastic flake feedstocks. This opens opportunities for recycling of feedstocks such as sorter reject streams, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fines and multi-layer tray waste. Ioniqa's glycolysis technology breaks down PET into monomers, which makes it much easier to remove impurities compared to isolating impurities from mixtures containing oligomers. In the PET glycolysis process, the ester bonds in PET are cleaved by mono ethylene glycol (MEG) to form Bis(2-Hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET). BHET is a monomer known in the PET-industry, as it is an intermediate in today's PET polymerisation processes that utilize oil based raw materials. The glycolysis process is typically performed at temperatures around the boiling point of MEG and in the presence of a catalyst. The four main steps that can be distinguished in the Ioniqa process are: reaction, inert and catalyst separation, purification and product isolation. Multi-layer trays add one more challenge due to the presence of other polymers in packaging, which Ioniqa's technology aims to remove prior to its core process.

Keywords: Chemical recycling, feedstocks composition and impurities, PET glycolysis.

1 Introduction

The general public awareness regarding the environment has increased significantly, and it has been on the agenda of governments since the early 1990s. This resulted in the publication of the Sustainable Development Goals by the United Nations (UN) and climate agreements like the Paris Climate Agreement [1]. Topics like global warming, deforestation, air pollution, and plastic waste have gained a lot of publicity within this context. However, the consumption of plastics packaging kept on increasing [2].

17.8 million tonnes of post-consumer plastic packaging were collected in Europe in 2018 with 17% of total plastic packaging being constructed from multi-layer material. Only 42% of the collected plastic packaging was recycled, while 39.5% was incinerated and 18.5% landfilled. This situation is still far from the objective to recycle 55% of the plastic by 2030 [3]. Mono-material plastic such as bottles can be recycled mechanically, but the multi-layer materials and other less pure streams are currently not recycled at all. Therefore, the multi-layer materials are the main focus of the H2020 MERLIN project [4].

This environmental challenge urges the need for more and improved recycling. Consequently, in the last decade there has been a lot of interest in chemical recycling. Chemical recycling can enable the use of low-quality feedstock to obtain high-quality materials without the material and quality losses encountered in mechanical recycling. Chemical recycling of PET can be divided into various processes; hydrolysis, methanolysis and glycolysis [5].

In 2009, Ioniqa was founded as a cleantech spin-off from Eindhoven University of Technology (The Netherlands). With the use of a smart magnetic catalyst, Ioniqa specializes in the chemical depolymerisation of PET by means of glycolysis. With an outlook on technology licencing, development of an industrially feasible process is progressing. Via this process, a circular economy for PET packaging can be obtained. The patented [6] catalytic depolymerisation process is specifically designed to upcycle post-consumer PET waste that is too contaminated for mechanical recycling and produce virgin like quality product.

2. The Ioniqa process

The Ioniqa process is centred around a glycolysis process, in which the PET polymer is depolymerised to BHET with the help of a magnetic catalyst, which is, due to its properties, easily recoverable after the reaction. After the glycolysis reaction has been completed, BHET is further purified to remove other reaction byproducts as well as contaminants which might be present in the waste plastic feedstock.

2.1 Glycolysis chemistry [7]

In the PET glycolysis process, the ester bonds in PET are cleaved by MEG to form BHET (Figure 1). This process is typically performed at temperatures around the boiling point of MEG and in the presence of a catalyst. Whether partial or full depolymerisation is achieved depends on reaction conditions, such as PET/MEG ratio and reaction time.

Figure 1: PET to BHET glycolysis reaction

The reaction mechanism of the glycolysis process is that of a (Brønsted base or Brønsted or Lewis acid catalysed) transesterification reaction. For the acid catalysed process, this consists of protonation followed by nucleophilic attack of the MEG on the PET and elimination of an alcohol (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Reaction mechanism for an acid catalysed transesterification reaction.

2.2 BHET-like by-products

The major by-products (Figure 3) present in a typical glycolysis process are mono-2-hydroxy-ethyl-terephthalate (MHET), BHET dimer, [2-(2-hydroxy-ethoxy)-ethyl]-2-hydroxy-ethyl-terephthalate (HEEHET) and bis-2-hydroxy-ethyl-iso-phthalate (BHEI). These are also known as “BHET-likes”.

Figure 3: Main impurity structures; BHET dimer, MHET, HEEHET, BHEI.

The amount of dimer present in the reaction mixture is mainly dependent on process parameters, such as reaction time and the used PET/MEG ratio. The higher this ratio, the more dimer (and sometimes longer oligomers) will remain. The presence of these short oligomers can never be completely prevented, due to the presence of a dynamic equilibrium with BHET and MEG (Figure 4). Since oligomers will repolymerize into PET, they have no effect on final PET quality and can therefore not be considered as an impurity. However, their presence may have an effect on the downstream processing and it is therefore important to be able to control their concentrations.

Figure 4: Equilibrium between BHET and its dimer. These compounds are in equilibrium with longer chains as well.

BHEI can be present in the reaction mixture due to the presence of isophthalic acid in the PET chain. This compound can be relatively easily removed during crystallization, which is the reason that Ioniqa's BHET only contains very small amounts of this compound. Unfortunately, it is impossible to remove all water from the process since it is formed with the side reaction forming HEEHET. HEEHET is formed by an etherification reaction, where a BHET molecule reacts with an MEG molecule to form a HEEHET molecule whilst releasing a water molecule. MHET is formed due to the presence of water in the reaction mixture. The presence of small amounts of water, unavoidable due to the side reaction producing HEEHET, will therefore cause small amounts of this MHET to be present. Although MHET will repolymerize into PET as well, and is therefore not considered as an impurity, it will lower the pH of the reaction mixture.

2.3 The purification process [7]

Ioniqa's glycolysis technology breaks down PET into BHET monomer, which makes it much easier to remove further impurities compared to depolymerisation reactions that produce oligomers. The four main steps that can be distinguished in the process are: reaction, inert and catalyst separation, purification and product isolation (Figure 5). The MEG, water and catalyst used in the process are recycled as much as possible. The final BHET product obtained is of sufficient quality to be polymerized into virgin-quality PET granulates.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of Ioniqa's glycolysis process, including the various impurity removal steps.

The process starts with feeding the reactor with low-grade, mixed-colour PET fractions that will react in a transesterification reaction with MEG. In its process Ioniqa employs heterogeneous, functionalized, magnetic nanoparticles to catalyse the glycolysis reaction. The surface of these magnetic particles is functionalized with a stabilizing component that makes them behave as a colloidal suspension of nanoscale superparamagnetic particles. This so-called “magnetic fluid” is a smart material that can be influenced by the presence of an external magnetic field. As a result, the catalyst complex possesses the functionality to be recovered from the reaction mixture and be recycled back into the process.

After the glycolysis reaction, the reaction mixture also contains, next to the desired BHET monomer, a variety of non-PET components that should be removed to obtain the final polymer-grade BHET product. In the first separation step, the non-PET remnants, mostly undissolved solid particles such as other polymers, metals, sand and paper, are removed using their difference in physical and chemical properties under the given process conditions. Hereafter the catalyst is separated from the reaction mixture. Non-PET remnants that dissolve and become sticky residues belong to the most challenging group of remnants. These types of remnants, or remnants that are present in very high concentrations in a specific feedstock stream might be isolated from the reaction mixture, or even before the reaction, in a dedicated step if this is proven to be more efficient.

Before recovering the BHET monomers, the residual colour components and additives from the PET feedstock are removed from the reaction mixture. The purified mother liquor is then cooled to crystallize the BHET product. These BHET crystals are separated from the mother liquor by filtration, washed and finally dried to the required specifications.

3 Feedstocks: from bottle to multi-layer tray and beyond

Working with waste plastic as a feedstock brings various chemical and technological challenges. Next to these challenges, a certain mindset needs to be accepted: plastic waste does not come with a detailed specification sheet. In the recycling of plastic waste, the challenge of feedstock variability is encountered on a global scale. Recyclable plastics can come from different sorting processes and originate from unknown sources. Even for the feedstocks coming from bottles, different shipments of feedstock with the same production code can have varying levels of impurities. This is very important to take into account during the design and development of chemical recycling processes. [8]

So, material will not be delivered with a well-defined specification sheet. To still have some guidance on the quality of materials, Vilaplana and Karlsson set forward a characterization of the quality of recycled plastics and feedstocks by three main properties (Figure 6) [9] which are explained in the text below the figure.

Figure 6: Parameters to identify the quality of recycled plastics (adapted from [9])

The first property is the degree of mixing (Figure 6, leftward point of the triangle), which is related to the quantity of contaminations with larger particle size that are present in polluted waste streams (“composition of the feed”). The composition of the feed is related to the sorting technique that has been applied to the collected material. Since mechanical recycling is applied on larger scale, sorters focus on achieving purity of PET flakes suitable for those processes. Density focused systems in either cyclones or tanks with paddles, optical sorting machines for polymer and colour recognition and techniques like eddy current separators for metal removal can be applied [10,11,12]. They all have in common that side streams, sorter rejects, are generated in those sorting processes. These sorter rejects are suitable feedstock for chemical recycling processes if they contain enough of a specific type of plastic. Ioniqa can handle sorter streams with high content of contaminants such as aluminium, wood or other plastics, for example PE, PVC and PP. The sorter rejects are, in general, an ideal feedstock for chemical recycling since they do not compete with mechanical recycling as they are considered a waste stream.

During their life cycle, plastics undergo various chemical and physical changes. These changes can occur due to thermo- and photo-degradation processes aided by oxidative reactions, which, for example, can result in lower intrinsic viscosities. The degree of degradation (Figure 6, right upper point of the triangle) is an important characteristic of plastic waste because it is directly correlated to the future performance of these polymers after mechanical recycling. For chemical recycling however, these degradation characteristics are of less importance since the plastics are returned to their monomer form during the depolymerisation process.

The last plastic waste quality characteristic is the presence of low molecular weight components (Figure 6, downward pointing point of the triangle). The list of such compounds in PET flakes can be quite extensive, therefore only the most important and common ones are discussed here. The first and most obvious components are solvent dyes in coloured PET flakes. Certain coloured PET granules are generally automatically deemed unfit for mechanical recycling as they result in unwanted colours or mixtures [13]. For chemical recycling however, it was found that colours do not influence the depolymerisation process. The second group of contaminants to consider consists of inorganic contaminants that are sometimes deliberately present in PET flakes. Examples are species such as antimony, cobalt and magnesium, originating from the PET polymerisation catalysts [14]. Another common inorganic contaminant is titanium dioxide [15], which is added to PET flakes as a pigment to induce turbidity and produce opaque PET bottles.

3.1 Beyond bottles: Multi-Layer Packaging

Multi-layer packaging refers to packaging composed out of different layers with each their own function. The outer layer may be present for printability and mechanical stability to the structure, whilst inner layers are mostly functional layers which can provide barrier properties to for example oxygen, moisture or light. The purpose of the functional layers is to increase the shelf life of food [16]. The multi-layer PET tray is a very common packaging solution for products such as cheese, meat and fish. PE combined with PET gives a rigid tray that is heat sealable with top foil [17]. Ethylene-vinyl alcohol copolymer (EVOH) is known for having some of the best barrier resistance to gases such as oxygen, nitrogen, and carbon dioxide which makes it good for packaging food and other perishable goods. EVOH loses its favourable gas barrier properties when exposed to moisture and for this reason, EVOH is often used in multilayer systems with materials such as PE, PP and PET, all of which have moisture barrier properties [18]. Within the H2020 MERLIN project (grant agreement number 101003883), Ioniqa learned that EVOH would be the major new contaminants when broadening the technology to this feedstock category. The PET|EVOH|PE tray [19] was found to be common. Since the layers in multi-layer materials can often not be easily removed from each other, traditional sorting methods are not able to produce a mono-material output suitable for mechanical recycling from those feedstocks.

Within the H2020 MERLIN project, Ioniqa is developing an additional process unit to extract the EVOH prior to the depolymerisation reaction. EVOH is a polymer with challenging properties in the reaction conditions as it causes significant fouling of equipment. By extracting EVOH upfront, that is, before the reaction, the core of Ioniqa's process stays the same and isolation and valorisation of EVOH remains possible

4 Conclusions

Plastic waste is a feedstock that comes without a very detailed composition- and datasheet. This paper points to the need of chemical recycling next to mechanical recycling processes, since large quantities of plastic waste are available in streams with many types of impurities. It can be concluded that chemical recycling is a technology that can handle feedstock with various impurities, but it can also deal with variations in feedstocks. This can be achieved by full depolymerisation of the PET material, followed by process steps that are focussed on removing all the non-PET materials based on differences in physical and chemical properties.

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